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Keweenaw Bay Indian Community Climate-Related Change Survey Report

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1. Introduction

Forests are fundamental to the sustenance of human life and livelihoods, serving as sources of food, water, shelter, and environmental services for countless communities worldwide (Trumbore et al., 2015). However, how these communities interact with forests, perceive their significance, and navigate the impacts of climate-related changes on forest ecosystems and associated livelihoods can vary significantly (Lawler and Bullock 2017; Domke et al., 2023).

Tribal communities view forests as much more than just natural resources. Forests are intertwined with their cultural identities, spiritual beliefs, and livelihood activities such as hunting, fishing, and gathering medicinal plants and food (Dockry et al., 2022). The relationships between Indigenous communities and forests are deeply rooted and cultivated over generations through the transmission of Traditional Ecological Knowledge (Gagnon et al., 2013). The Keweenaw Bay Indian Community (KBIC), a Native American community located along Lake Superior in Michigan's Upper Peninsula, exemplifies this profound connection. As the state's largest reservation, KBIC is one of many tribes with centuries-old traditional and spiritual ties to the land, waters, fish, and wildlife. Many Tribal members today practice subsistence and commercial harvesting as it has been lived through the generations. These Tribal practices are also protected by a land cession treaty between the Chippewa and the federal government, the 1842 Treaty of La Pointe. According to the treaty, the bands intentionally reserved their rights to fish, hunt, and gather on ceded territories. For many generations, the Ojibwa of KBIC have actively engaged in long-term planning and stewardship of the forest ecosystem while balancing the people's survivance, livelihood, and resilience.

On the other hand, non-Tribal communities may have less direct cultural ties to forests (Dockry et al., 2022). Their interactions with forests are often shaped by socioeconomic factors like household size and income (Shishany et al., 2020; Darboe et al., 2023; Chishaleshale et al., 2024). For instance, socioeconomic necessity often drives direct resource extraction. Chishaleshale et al. (2024) found that larger households collect more forest products to meet greater subsistence needs, while Darboe et al. (2023) noted that communities in Gambia prioritized material goods like timber and fuelwood over non-material benefits. In contrast, wealthier households often derive value from forests indirectly. According to Lang et al. (2023), the financial benefits of conservation, such as increased property values, disproportionately flow to wealthier households, highlighting a different form of forest reliance based on economic advantage rather than daily necessity.

Increasing climate-induced extreme weather events such as hurricanes, droughts, and floods pose significant threats to both Tribal and non-Tribal communities such as resulting in loss of life, destruction of infrastructure and property, and disruption of economic activities (Sahu et al., 2022). However, Indigenous groups are disproportionately impacted by these climate instability effects and are among the most vulnerable populations in the world (National Wildlife Federation, 2011; STACCWG, 2021). The heightened susceptibility of Indigenous communities stems from several key factors. First, many Indigenous peoples reside in relatively isolated, rural, and environmentally precarious areas like coastlines, small islands, arctic regions, rainforests, and drylands (Fritze et al., 2008; Whyte et al., 2023). These geographical marginal areas are limited in their access to resources and infrastructure and are often exposed to climate hazards such as sea-level rise, droughts, floods, and wildfires, which exacerbates the vulnerability of Indigenous communities to the impacts of climate change (McMichael et al., 2012; Whyte

et al., 2023). Secondly, Tribal lands often consist of a fragmented land base with checkerboarded ownership or are confined within limited reservations, which complicates the management and adaptation efforts (National Wildlife Federation, 2011). Finally, Indigenous livelihoods, cultural practices, and ceremonies are often tied to specific species or ecosystems, disruptions to these systems jeopardize Indigenous ways of life, and their knowledge systems, and put the cultural survival of Tribal nations at risk (Whyte et al., 2023).

Public engagement is the first crucial step in incorporating people's interests, concerns, and needs (Khatibi et al., 2021). In order to ensure the relevance of policy legitimacy and build trust with communities, there is an urgent need for inclusive, community-driven research that amplifies the voices and lived experiences of those most affected by climate-induced changes to forest ecosystems. Centering Indigenous voices in research and decision-making is also essential for respecting cultural traditions, leveraging traditional ecological knowledge for sustainable management, upholding self-determination rights, and promoting equitable, culturally relevant policies (Whyte, 2018; Erickson et al., 2022). Aligning with the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, this participatory approach fosters cross-cultural dialogue supporting collaborative solutions grounded in diverse knowledge systems and values (Whyte, 2018).

This study was part of a broader research project "Bridging Indigenous and Western Sciences for Resilience, Livelihood, and Stewardship Planning: An Ojibwa Forest Ecosystem Characterization," funded by the USDA National Institute of Food and Agriculture McIntire-Stennis and the National Science Foundation (award #7001323). Conducted in partnership with the KBIC and following KBIC Research Guidance (2023), this study aims to understand the perspectives of Tribal and non-Tribal individuals on their relationships with forest ecosystems and their experiences with climate-related change events. The KBIC Natural Resources Department and Forestry Department jointly collaborated in developing and designing the study. Four research questions were:

- (1) What are the forest interactions of Tribal and non-Tribal people?
- (2) How are forests important to the well-being of Tribal and non-Tribal people?
- (3) How do climate-related changes influence the livelihood and cultural aspects of Tribal and non-Tribal people?
- (4) What are the concerns and hopes of local communities for the future of forests?

By examining these questions through a community-directed research approach, this study aims to deepen the understanding of the multifaceted roles that forests play in sustaining the lives, livelihoods, and cultures of both Tribal and non-Tribal peoples. Further, it also examines the impacts of climate-related changes on the culture and livelihoods across these groups. The findings aim to guide the development of inclusive natural resource policies, climate adaptation strategies, and forest stewardship practices that accommodates diverse needs while respecting the rights, values, and aspirations of all stakeholders confronting the escalating challenges of environmental change.

2. Methods

2.1. Survey design

A survey was designed as a convenience sample to assess the knowledge and perception of forest roles, climate-related change, and the effect of climate change on livelihood and cultural aspects of both Tribal and non-Tribal people (Appendix A-Questionnaires). On the header of each questionnaire, an introduction was included to inform the participants with the aim of the study and to obtain consent. The survey was composed of eight questions in total. The demographic characteristics of participants were assessed in the first three questions (Question 1 – 3) and included Tribal affiliation, county/state of residence, and age. All question and answer options were written in English.

Behavior assessment. One question (Question 4) composed of 12 items captured the participant's experience on their interactions with forests in the last year. The answer options were according to a five-point Likert scale (weekly, biweekly, monthly, bimonthly, once a year) along with the not applicable option.

Perception assessment. First, participants were asked to rate (on a scale of 10) the importance of forests to their cultural aspects and livelihood activities, which are composed of 9 items (Question 5). Next, one question composed of 18 items asking participants to identify the changes in the landscape in their community during the last five years (Question 6). The answers included four options: decrease, stay the same, increase, and not sure. After that, one question (Question 7) composed of 12 items asking for their opinions on how the changes in the landscape influence their ability for cultural and livelihood activities compared with the last five years. The answer options followed a five-point Likert scale (much better, somewhat better, stayed the same, somewhat worse, much worse) along with the not applicable option. Finally, an open-ended question (Question 8) asked participants to list their biggest concerns and/or hopes for the future of the forests.

2.2. Ethical statement

The survey and questionnaires were approved by Michigan Technological University Institutional Review Board (IRB) and were designed to ensure confidentiality and anonymity of the participants. Prior to participating in this study, verbal consent was obtained from all participants. Participants were informed of what they were being asked to do; their participation was completely voluntary, there was no risk involved, and could withdraw their consent at any time.

2.3. Data collection

The survey was conducted at the KBIC summer powwow for two days. KBIC Tribal leadership coordinated our presence by setting up our booth to recruit participants. The booth included a tent, a table presented with survey questionnaires and KBIC Natural Resources Department's brochures, a banner with information about research partnership between KBIC and Michigan Technological University, a table with three drawing prizes including books, jams, kimchi, coffee, tea, mugs, sun hat as incentives to participants, and a table with pen, crayons, coloring pictures, and candies for children.

Two or more team members were present at the booth throughout the survey to recruit study participants. Team members engaged with anyone passing by the booth with a greeting and a brief introduction about the forest relationship and climate-related change survey and that they would be eligible to enter a drawing to win one of three prizes if they completed the form. The team also reminded participants about

the questionnaire's length, how long it would take to complete, and addressed any questions or provided additional information as needed.

2.4. Data analysis

After gathering all the surveys, the data were imported into an Excel spreadsheet. We excluded surveys submitted by individuals under 18 years of age and surveys where questions 4-7 were not completely answered. The data were then analyzed and visualized using RStudio (version 2024.04.0 Build 735) and Microsoft Excel.

Given that this study is exploratory in nature and aimed at gaining initial insights, descriptive statistical analysis was more appropriate than predictive analyses for interpreting the results. Furthermore, to ensure the reliability of the multi-item scales used to assess interaction with forests (Q4), observations of changes in forest landscapes (Q5), perceptions of forest importance (Q6), and the influence of climate-related changes (Q7), internal consistency was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha (Taber, 2017).

Cronbach's alpha is often used to assess the degree to which a set of items measures a single latent construct, with values ranging from 0 to 1 (George and Mallery, 2003). Generally, a Cronbach's alpha of 0.70 or higher is considered acceptable, while values between 0.60 and 0.70 suggest questionable reliability. Values below 0.60 may indicate poor internal consistency and suggest the need for scale refinement (George and Mallery, 2003). As this study is exploratory, slightly lower Cronbach's alpha values are considered acceptable for identifying preliminary trends and informing future research directions (Taber, 2017).

The following findings are presented to address research questions of this study.

3. Results

The results will be presented in four primary parts as follows: Participants characteristics, Forest interactions (**research question 1**), Forest values (**research question 2**), Climate-related change impacts (**research question 3**), Concerns and hopes to forest (**research question 4**).

3.1. Participants characteristics

A total of 265 responses were collected. We excluded 9 respondents who were under 18 years old and 24 who did not complete Questions 4 to 7.

Our data included 232 participants, with 47.5% (n = 110) being Tribal participants and 52.5% (n = 122) from non-Tribal participants. In the Tribal group, the majority at 21.5% (n = 50) were from KBIC, followed by 16% (n = 37) from other Tribal nations outside of Michigan, and 10% (n = 23) were from Tribal nations within Michigan. In the non-Tribal group, Michigan residents represent the largest at 42.2% (n = 98), followed by 10.3% (n = 24) were from other states. Figure 3.1 shows the groups distributions by survey respondents.

Figure 3.1. Surveyed participants' group by Tribal affiliation and location of residence

In terms of their residing state, the majority, at 74.6% (n = 173), were from Michigan. This was followed by Wisconsin at 7.8% (n=18), Illinois at 4% (n=10), and Minnesota also at 4 % (n=10). The median and mean age were 43.5 and 39 years old respectively, with all ages ranging from 18 to 85 years. A distribution of residing states and age of participants is listed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Distribution of residing states and age of participants

	Non-Tribal group (n = 122)	Tribal group (n = 110)	Overall (n = 232)
State			
Alaska	1 (0.8%)	1 (0.9%)	2 (0.9%)
Illinois	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)	10 (4.3%)
Michigan	99 (81.1%)	75 (68.2%)	174 (75.0%)
Minnesota	4 (3.3%)	6 (5.5%)	10 (4.3%)
Ohio	1 (0.8%)	2 (1.8%)	3 (1.3%)
Virginia	2 (1.6%)	0 (0%)	2 (0.9%)
Wisconsin	6 (4.9%)	12 (10.9%)	18 (7.8%)
California	0 (0%)	2 (1.8%)	2 (0.9%)
Canada	0 (0%)	6 (5.5%)	6 (2.6%)
Massachusetts	0 (0%)	1 (0.9%)	1 (0.4%)
New Mexico	0 (0%)	1 (0.9%)	1 (0.4%)
Missing	3 (2.5%)	0 (0%)	3 (1.3%)
Age			
Mean (SD)	44.1 (19.3)	42.9 (17.8)	43.5 (18.6)
Median [Min, Max]	40.0 [18.0, 85.0]	39.0 [18.0, 81.0]	39.0 [18.0, 85.0]
Missing	11 (9.0%)	12 (10.9%)	23 (9.9%)

3.2. Frequency of forest interactions

Participants rated their frequencies of 11 forest-related activities on a six-point Likert scale (weekly, biweekly, monthly, bimonthly, once a year, and *not applicable*). Cronbach's alpha for the frequency of forest interactions was 0.61 (see Appendix B). Although a Cronbach's alpha above 0.7 is often desired, 0.61 is acceptable in this context due to diversity of activities included (i.e., recreation, hunting, gathering medicinal plants). Additionally, the reliability score of 0.61 can also be explained by differences in activity patterns between Tribal and non-Tribal participants. Tribal participants engaged more frequently in culturally and traditionally significant activities, such as hunting, making traditional ceremonial items and gathering medicinal plants, thus creating the diverse patterns of forest usage.

In general, a majority of participants engaged with the forest for recreation (90%) and spiritual well-being and personal enrichment (81%). Other activities included gathering materials for non-commercial activities (70%), collecting plants for traditional food or drink (66%), sharing knowledge and skills with others (65%), fishing (61%), medicinal plants gathering (44%), hunting (40%), making traditional/ceremonial items for non-commercial use (39%), harvesting materials for commercial activity (10%), and trapping (12%). Two respondents added two activities: ecological restoration and participating in a faith community. Further, there were differences in the frequencies of forest-related activities between Tribal and non-Tribal participants. However, only making traditional or ceremonial items appeared to be significantly different ($p < 0.001$). The response results are presented in Figure 3.2 and Appendix C-Table 3.2.

Hunting, Fishing, and Trapping: Tribal participants reported higher overall engagement in hunting (46% vs. 34% non-Tribal), fishing (65% vs. 57%), and trapping (15% vs. 9%). However, non-Tribal

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participants showed slightly higher weekly participation in hunting (8% vs. 6%) and fishing (11% vs. 8%). Most participants in both groups reported engaging in these activities only once a year or bimonthly.

Figure 3.2. Frequency of visiting forests for different purposes between Tribal and non-Tribal groups and p values (Significant codes: 0‘***’ 0.001‘***’ 0.01‘**’).

Gathering medicinal plants and Collecting plants for traditional food or drink: On average, Tribal participants more frequently gathered medicinal plants (55% vs. 34%) and collected plants for traditional food or drink (70% vs. 62%) compared to non-Tribal participants.

Making traditional ceremonial items (non-commercial use): Engagement in this activity was significantly higher among Tribal participants (57% vs. 22%, $p < 0.001$). Both groups reported participation mainly on a monthly, bimonthly, or annual basis.

Gathering materials for non-commercial activities and for commercial activities: On average, Tribal participants engage in both activities more than non-Tribal participants, with the percentage of Tribal groups being 73% and 37% respectively compared to 68% and 24% reported by non-Tribal group. Both groups reported doing these activities either monthly, bimonthly, or once a year basis.

Recreation, Spiritual well-being, and personal enrichment, and Sharing knowledge and skills with others: On average, non-Tribal participants were more likely to report engaging in recreation (93% vs. 85%), while Tribal participants reported higher engagement in spiritual well-being and personal enrichment (85% vs. 79%) and in sharing knowledge and skills with others (70% vs. 61%). These activities were most often done on a weekly basis.

In summary, there are some different patterns of forest usage between Tribal and non-Tribal groups. While Tribal participants reported higher frequencies for culturally significant activities like making ceremonial and traditional items, hunting, fishing, and gathering plants, non-Tribal participants visited forests more frequently for recreational purposes. Regarding **research question 1**, these differences indicate that forest management strategies must accommodate both leisure-based and cultural and traditional essential uses.

3.3. Importance of forests

Participants rated the importance of forests to eight aspects of their livelihood and cultural practices on a scale from 1 (not at all important) to 10 (extremely important). Cronbach's alpha for these ratings was 0.77 (see Appendix B), indicating good internal consistency.

In general, both Tribal and non-Tribal groups considered forests highly important across most categories. The highest ratings were for accessing fresh air and clean water (mean = 9.35, median = 10), opportunities for recreation (9.09, 10), and spiritual well-being and personal enrichment (8.81, 10). These were followed by identity and cultural heritage (8.2, 10), subsistence sources (7.75, 10), ability to share knowledge and skills (7.65, 9), medicinal sources (7.08, 10), and accessing for income source from commercial activity (6.66, 10). One respondent additionally noted that forests were important to their career. Additionally, there were differences between the Tribal and non-Tribal groups' ratings, especially in identity and cultural heritage ($p = 0.004$), ability to share knowledge and skills ($p = 0.029$) and accessing income source from commercial activity ($p = 0.048$). Figure 3.2 and Appendix C-Table 3.2 provide participants' rating responses in detail.

Identity and cultural heritage: Tribal participants rated the importance of forests for their identity and cultural heritage significantly higher than non-Tribal participants ($p = 0.004$). The majority of Tribal respondents (65%) rated forests as extremely important (rating of 10) for this aspect, compared to 37% of non-Tribal respondents. On the other hand, 22.1% of non-Tribal respondents rated below 6 for this aspect, compared to 8.1% of Tribal respondents.

Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment: There was no significant difference between the two groups in rating this aspect. However, a higher percentage of Tribal participants (67%) considered forests as extremely important (rating of 10) compared to non-Tribal participants (52%).

Ability to share knowledge and skills: Tribal participants rated the importance of forests for their ability to share knowledge and skills significantly higher than non-Tribal participants ($p = 0.029$). The percentage of Tribal respondents who gave a rating of 10 was 50% compared to 30% of non-Tribal respondents.

Access to fresh air and clean water, opportunities for recreation: Both groups gave very high ratings, with Tribal participants slightly more likely to rate forests as extremely important for fresh air and clean water (80% vs. 73%), while recreation ratings were nearly identical (66% vs. 67%).

Access to medicinal sources and income sources from commercial activity: There was a marginally significant difference between the two groups ($p = 0.053$ and $p = 0.048$), with Tribal participants rating the forests as extremely important for both medicinal sources and income source higher than non-Tribal participants. The percentage of Tribal respondents giving a rating of 10 was 55% and 34%, compared to 30% and 24%, respectively.

Regarding **research question 2**, forests support well-being through two pathways. Both Tribal and non-Tribal participants emphasized the critical importance of forests, particularly for clean air, clean water, recreation, and spiritual well-being. Tribal participants placed significantly greater importance on forests for cultural identity and knowledge-sharing, and also rated forests higher for medicinal and commercial income sources. This dual dependency means that protecting Tribal well-being requires forest policies that address both ecological services and cultural-economic systems.

Replies to Q5: On a scale from 1 to 10, how important are forests to your...?

1 = Not at all important, 10 = Extremely important; 99 = Not applicable

Figure 3.2. Importance of forests to livelihood and cultural aspects of Tribal and non-Tribal groups with p values (Significant codes: 0‘***’ 0.001‘***’ 0.01‘*’).

3.4. Influence of climate-related change

Participants were asked to indicate if they had noticed changes in 17 aspects of the landscape in their community over the last five years using a four-point scale (decrease, stayed the same, increase, and not sure). They were then asked to rate how those changes have impacted their ability to engage in various livelihood activities and cultural practices, compared to previous years, using a six-point scale (much worse, somewhat worse, stayed the same, somewhat better, much better, and not applicable). Therefore, in this section, we first present information about the reported landscape changes, followed by the perceived impacts of those changes on the participants.

3.4.1. *Landscape observations*

In the landscape observations, we organized them into three categories: a) observations related to forest cover and plants, b) observations related to wildlife, fish, and insects, c) observations related to weather patterns and human activities. The respondents' answers for each aspect are provided in Appendix-Table 3.4.1.

a) Observations related to forest cover and plants.

The Cronbach's alpha for observations related to forest cover and plants was 0.91, indicating a high level of internal consistency (see Appendix B).

Overall, more than 47% of participants reported changes in the forest cover and plants in their communities in the last five years. The highest percentage of participants (67%) noticed changes in forest cover, followed by 55% observed changes in berries, 44% in birch and maple, 41% in cedar, and 40% in balsam fir. There was a significant difference between Tribal and non-Tribal participants noticing changes in berries ($p = 0.026$). Figure 3.4.1a presents the changes in forest cover and plants reported by participants.

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Replies to Q6: In the last five years, what changes on the landscape did you notice in your community?

a) Observations related to forest and plants

Figure 3.4.1a Changes in landscape reported by participants related to forest cover and plants and p values (Significant codes: 0‘****’ 0.001‘***’ 0.01‘*’).

Forest cover: On average, a majority of respondents reported either a decrease or no change in forest cover in the past five years. There were no differences between Tribal (35% for a decrease and 25% for no change) and non-Tribal (36% for a decrease and 32% for no change) participants in observing this landscape aspect.

Cedar, Birch, Balsam fir, and Maple: Similarly, the majority of participants in both groups reported either a decrease or no change in trends for cedar, birch, balsam fir, and maple populations. The average percentage for a decrease was 20%, 25%, 11%, and 11% respectively, while staying the same was at 33%, 31%, 36%, and 33%.

Berries: Although the percentages of Tribal and non-Tribal participants reported changes in berry populations might appear similar, their response patterns were significantly different ($p = 0.026$). A higher percentage of Tribal participants (33%) reported a decrease in berries. While a higher percentage of non-Tribal participants (38%) reported no change in trend.

In summary, approximately half of participants observed changes in forest vegetation over the past five years. Forest cover changes were the most widely reported, with about one-third noting decreases across both groups. The most notable difference was that Tribal participants observed more declines in berry populations compared to non-Tribal participants, who generally reported berry populations as stable.

b) Observations related to wildlife, fish, and insects.

The Cronbach's alpha for observations related to wildlife, fish, and insects was 0.78, indicating a good level of internal consistency (see Appendix B).

Overall, 49% of participants reported changes in the wildlife, fish, and insects in their communities in the last five years. The highest percentage of participants (67%) noticed changes in deer population, followed by 62% observed changes in insects, 48% in fish populations in streams, 37% in bear, and 34% in ruffed grouse. Three respondents reported an increase in skunks, rabbits, and birds. There was a significant difference between Tribal and non-Tribal participants noticing changes in fish populations in streams ($p = 0.033$). Figure 3.4.1b presents the changes in wildlife, fish, and insects reported by participants.

Bear: Most participants (21%) reported no change in bear populations. However, more participants (18%) in the Tribal group reported an increase in bear populations, compared to 9.8% of non-Tribal participants. While most of the non-Tribal participants (25%) reported no change in trend.

Deer: On average, most participants (31%) reported an increase in deer populations, with 33% of non-Tribal participants and 30% of Tribal participants. Followed by 27% of participants reported no change in the population trend, with similar proportions among Tribal (27%) and non-Tribal (26%) participants.

Ruffed grouse: Both groups reported similar observations regarding changes in ruffed grouse populations, with the majority of participants (22%) reported no change trend.

Fish population in streams: There was a significant difference ($p = 0.033$) between the two groups in their observations of changes in fish populations in streams. A slightly higher percentage of Tribal participants (33%) reported a decrease in fish populations compared to 30% of non-Tribal participants. While non-Tribal participants had a higher percentage reporting no change (25%), compared to 15% of Tribal participants.

Insects: On average, most participants (41%) reported an increase in insect populations, with no difference across the two groups.

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Replies to Q6: In the last five years, what changes on the landscape did you notice in your community?

b) Observations related to wildlife, fish, and insects

Figure 3.4.1b. Changes in landscape reported by participants related to wildlife, fish, and insects and p values (Significant codes: 0***' 0.001'***' 0.01'**').

In summary, about half of participants observed changes in wildlife and insect populations over the past five years. Deer populations changes were most commonly reported, followed by insects. The most notable difference between two groups was Tribal participants reported more decreases and fewer “no change” responses in fish population than non-Tribal participants.

c) Observations related to weather patterns and human activities.

The Cronbach’s alpha for observations related to weather patterns and human activities was 0.71, indicating a good level of internal consistency (see Appendix B).

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Overall, 74.5% of participants reported changes in the weather patterns and human activities in their communities in the last five years. The highest percentage of participants (87%) noticed changes in temperature, followed by 86% observed changes in snowfall, 76% in water levels in streams, 75% in flooding, 73% in human activities, and 63% in soil erosion. Figure 3.4.1c presents the participants' answers for each item.

Temperature, flooding, and soil erosion: The majority of participants observed an increase in temperature, flooding, and soil erosion over the last five years, with a percentage of 65%, 50%, and 47% respectively. Around 39%, 26%, and 17% stated that temperatures, flooding, and soil erosion, respectively, stayed the same during this period. There were no differences between the two groups in identifying these changes.

Water level in streams: There was a marginally significant difference between the two groups in their observations of changes in water levels in streams. A higher percentage of Tribal participants (38%) reported an increase in water levels compared to non-Tribal participants (25%). Additionally, more non-Tribal participants (27%) observed a decrease in water levels compared to Tribal participants (23%).

Snowfall: Both groups reported similar observations regarding changes in snowfall, with around 37-38% of participants indicating a decrease in snowfall. However, a higher percentage of Tribal participants (25%) observed an increase in snowfall compared to non-Tribal participants (21%).

Human activities: Both groups reported similar observations regarding changes in human activities, with around 52-56% of participants indicating an increase in human activities over the last five years.

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Replies to Q6: In the last five years, what changes on the landscape did you notice in your community?

c) Observations related to weather patterns and human activities

Figure 3.4.1c. Changes in landscape reported by participants related to weather patterns and human activities and p values (Significant codes: 0‘***’ 0.001‘**’ 0.01‘*’).

In summary, approximately 75% of participants observed environmental changes in their communities over the past five years, with consensus around increasing temperatures and human activities, and decreasing snowfall. While Tribal and non-Tribal groups reported similar patterns in most categories, Tribal participants observed more increases in water levels in streams.

3.4.2. Influence of climate-related changes on respondents’ livelihoods and cultural aspects

The Cronbach’s alpha for influence of climate-related changes on livelihoods and cultural aspects was 0.86, indicated high internal consistency (see Appendix B).

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Figure 3.4.2 and the Appendix-Table 3.4.2 present the perceived influence of climate-related changes on 11 livelihood and cultural aspects among Tribal and non-Tribal participants. There was a significant difference between the two groups in participants' ability for medicinal plants gathering ($p = 0.006$) and gathering materials for making traditional items ($p = 0.018$).

Figure 3.4.2. Influence of climate-related changes on different livelihood and cultural aspects across Tribal and non-Tribal groups and p values (Significant codes: 0**** 0.001*** 0.01**).

Hunting, Fishing, and Trapping: On average, most participants reported no influence of landscape changes on hunting (23%), fishing (30%), or trapping (14%) abilities. However, there was a marginally significant difference ($p = 0.057$) in hunting between groups, with 18% of Tribal participants reporting somewhat worse impacts compared to 11% of non-Tribal participants.

Gathering medicinal plants and Collecting plants for traditional food or drink: On average, most participants perceived no change in ability to gather medicinal plants (24%) or traditional food/drink plants (34%). However, Tribal participants were significantly more likely (23%) to report somewhat worse impacts on medicinal plant gathering compared to non-Tribal participants (9.8%) ($p = 0.006$).

Making traditional ceremonial items (non-commercial use): On average, most participants perceived no change in their ability to make traditional ceremonial items (25%). However, Tribal participants were significantly more likely (15%) to report somewhat worse impacts compared to non-Tribal participants (5.7%) ($p = 0.018$).

Gathering materials for non-commercial activities and for commercial activities: On average, most participants reported no change in gathering for non-commercial (36%) or commercial (20%) activities. However, a slightly higher percentage of Tribal participants felt that climate-related changes had a somewhat worse impact on their ability to gather materials for both activities (16% and 11%) compared to non-Tribal participants (11% and 7.4%).

Recreation, Spiritual well-being, and personal enrichment, and Sharing knowledge and skills with others: On average, most participants perceived no change in their ability for recreation activities (39%), for spiritual well-being and personal enrichment activities (39%), and for sharing knowledge and skills with others (33%). However, a slightly higher percentage of Tribal participants (11% and 13%) felt that climate-related changes had much better effects on their spiritual well-being and personal enrichment and sharing knowledge and skills with others compared to non-Tribal participants (6.6% and 4.1%).

In summary, most participants perceived no major changes in their livelihoods and cultural practices due to climate-related changes. However, Tribal participants significantly reported more negative impacts on gathering medicinal plants and materials for traditional items. Although it was not significant, Tribal participants perceived climate-related changes as enhancing their spiritual well-being and ability to share knowledge and skills than non-Tribal participants.

Regarding **research question 3**, community members widely observed environmental change, but their impacts were uneven. Non-Tribal participants tended to frame changes in environmental or recreational terms, whereas Tribal participants felt stronger disruptions to culturally rooted practices. Statistically significant differences were seen in berries, fish populations, medicinal plants, and traditional materials-species and resources closely tied to Tribal diets, ceremonies, and medicines. The practical meaning is that climate change is not only an environmental challenge but also a cultural one, where even small ecological shifts can have outsized consequences for those whose traditions and livelihoods are directly tied to the land.

3.5. Concerns and Hopes for forests

3.5.1. Concern for forests

Eighty-four respondents expressed concerns about the present and future state of forests, wildlife populations, and the environment. They cited human activities as a significant contributing factor. Most focused on the adverse impacts of climate change on the well-being of various species, long-term biodiversity, and the potential loss of forests for future generations. Figure 3.5.1 provides a word cloud that highlights various concerns for forests by surveyed respondents.

Figure 3.5.1. Concerns for the forests by surveyed respondents

- Climate-related concerns

Climate change emerged as the predominant concern across both demographic groups, though with varying emphasis and framing. Among non-Tribal respondents, climate-related concerns represented 36% of all expressed concerns (16 of 45 responses), making it the most frequently cited issue. Respondents described concerns ranging from broad impacts—"my biggest concerns are climate change and deforestation"—to specific manifestations such as "drought, increasing temperature killing trees" and "climate change, droughts, wildfire."

Tribal respondents expressed climate concerns in 20% of cases (8 of 40 responses), often connecting these changes to cultural and subsistence practices. Notable responses included concerns about reaching "a point of no return with our emissions" and observations about "warming temperature affect on animals and human life." One tribal respondent specifically noted the vulnerability of culturally significant species: "Climate change and sustainability-migration of sensitive species such as maple (sugar), black ash, etc."

- Forest management and harvesting practices

Deforestation and overcutting concerns were prominent across both groups, representing 27% of non-tribal concerns (12 of 45) and 15% of tribal concerns (6 of 40). Non-tribal respondents frequently expressed concerns about commercial practices, with comments such as "so much clear-cutting. Climate change, warm weather effect on forests. So much new housing and commercial development in natural forest" and "deforestation - man's misuse."

Tribal perspectives on harvesting reflected deeper concerns about treaty rights and sustainable practices. One respondent noted that "overharvesting influences all species on the landscape including U.S. Our

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treaty rights have already been impacted by deforestation." Another expressed concern about "big companies cut too much trees" and emphasized the need for "proper land management appropriate deforestation obtaining permission from tribal communities or land owners before clear cutting."

- Forest health and ecosystem integrity

Forest health concerns, including disease, pests, and wildfire, were more prominent among non-tribal respondents (29% of concerns, 13 of 45) compared to tribal respondents (13% of concerns, 5 of 40). Non-tribal respondents frequently cited specific threats such as "invasive species," "forest fires, over harvesting," and "disease in trees (maple, oak)." One respondent detailed the complexity of these issues: "monoculture of maple caused emerald ash borer in the maple population."

Tribal respondents expressed forest health concerns with emphasis on drought impacts and species-specific vulnerabilities. Notable concerns included "we are experiencing a really bad drought," "trees dying," and specific mentions of culturally important species: "concerned about black ash, wild rice, clean water, deer health."

- Access rights and cultural preservation

Access and cultural rights concerns revealed differences between groups. While representing 11% of non-tribal concerns (5 of 45), these issues constituted 10% of tribal concerns (4 of 40) but carried significantly different meanings. Non-tribal concerns focused primarily on recreational access and privatization: "privatization of public land," "land access in Keweenaw county has been reduced due to new ownership," and desires for "more access to forests without payment."

Tribal concerns centered on fundamental cultural and subsistence rights. One respondent described losing access to traditional gathering areas: "Much of the Huron is not monitored and is run by lampers (free camping). My familys generational blueberry picking spot was picked through by campers, can't practice gathering rights." Another expressed broader cultural concerns: "biggest concern is losing our young people and cultures." The intersection of access and cultural practice was evident in concerns about "not having access to cultural practices" and "privatization, decreasing access because of trail/road erosion."

- Human impact and development pressures

Human impact concerns were expressed by 22% of non-tribal respondents (10 of 45) and 18% of tribal respondents (7 of 40). Non-tribal responses often focused on development pressure and mismanagement: "so much new housing and commercial development in natural forest," "development, misuse, mismanagement," and "mechanical overuse-on trail and off trails."

Tribal respondents emphasized disrespectful human behavior and systemic issues: "people's lack of respect for our land and water. It seems to be a 'use and abuse' mentality," "people leaving old campsites and garbage in the forests," and concerns about "brown sites and pollution in soil including garbage and salt which mutate plant babies and dehydrate plants."

- Species and wildlife concerns

Wildlife and species concerns were equally prominent between groups, with 22% of non-tribal concerns (10 of 45) and 18% of tribal concerns (7 of 40) addressing these issues. Non-tribal respondents focused

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on population dynamics and habitat: "decreasing of deer population," "climate change and human encroachment may cause reduce in wildlife populations," and "invasive species, development, not having access to cultural practices, decrease in overall well-being of species and biodiversity."

Tribal perspectives often connected wildlife concerns to broader ecosystem health and traditional practices: "natural wildlife not being available to pass on to my children," and detailed observations about ecosystem changes: "the future of wolf and deer management with emphasis on wolf hunting negatively impacting our natural ecology with fewer wolves and increase of deer with rising temperature. I fear for CWD and EHD spread to the U.P."

- Water quality and pollution

Water and pollution concerns were more prominent among Tribal respondents (18% of concerns, 7 of 40) compared to non-Tribal respondents (9% of concerns, 4 of 45). Tribal concerns often emphasized the connection between water quality and cultural practices: "to keep our waters clean and accessible to our native communities," and "the spraying of pesticides on farm land and the effect on the environment in the long run."

Non-Tribal water concerns focused more on general environmental contamination: "general climate change, deforestation and contamination through chemicals," "pollution and dumping in protected areas," and "rising water temperature."

3.5.2. *Hopes for the future of forests*

There were 106 respondents who expressed their aspirations for the future of forests. The majority emphasized sustainable management practices, forest protection, increased public access, and respect for Indigenous traditions in forest management. The overarching goal is to maintain healthy forests for the benefit and enjoyment of future generations while balancing ecological conservation with human use. Figure 3.5.2 presents a word cloud highlighting the central message of hope for the future of forests.

- Preservation and protection

Both groups strongly emphasized forest preservation, though with different framings. Non-Tribal hopes frequently focused on conservation outcomes: "forests are preserved and protected," "preservation of forests," and "I hope we are able to protect forests better." The emphasis was often on maintaining current forest conditions: "forests stay the same" appeared multiple times in non-Tribal responses.

Tribal hopes for preservation often connected to cultural continuity and intergenerational responsibility: "we have forests for our future generations," "preservation, harvesting for all future generation," and "sustainability of the forests for the future generations." One respondent expressed hope to "sustain and improve health of our relatives (all living beings)," reflecting Indigenous concepts of kinship with natural systems.

Figure 3.5.2. Hopes for the future of forests by surveyed respondents

- Sustainable management and restoration

Sustainable management hopes were expressed across both groups but with different emphases. Non-Tribal respondents focused on technical management approaches: "forest sustainable harvest, cutting," "conservation. Replacing trees after harvest," and "biodiversity, wildfire prevention, effective management."

Tribal hopes emphasized holistic and culturally appropriate management: "obviously sustainable harvesting is a must!!" "maintaining resources in a sustainable manner so we don't lose it for future generation," and "proper land management appropriate deforestation obtaining permission from Tribal communities or land owners before clear cutting."

- Education and cultural connection

Educational hopes were expressed by both groups but reflected different priorities. Non-Tribal respondents hoped for increased environmental awareness: "hopes to increase in education on cultural significance of forests/nature," "sustainable harvest and more public education," and "getting more people involved with environmental causes."

Tribal educational hopes centered on cultural transmission and respect: "learn 7 grandfather teachings," "I hope all forests stay safe and keep the young people involved in the nature," and "hope that the next generation get outdoors." One respondent specifically hoped for "more people will become aware and take responsibility to land stewardship and protecting water and plant and animal relatives and land back."

- Access and equity

Access-related hopes revealed the different needs and perspectives of each group. Non-Tribal hopes often focused on recreational access: "more people will have access to the outdoors," "hope forest more accessible," and "make public access easier access through improved trails, maps, etc."

Tribal access hopes emphasized cultural rights and equity: "proper management and access for low-income individuals," "increase access to lakes/stream," and hopes for "federal-Tribal collaboration; slowing capitalism."

Regarding **research question 4**, the analysis reveals both convergent concerns about climate change and forest health, and divergent perspectives rooted in different relationships to forest landscapes. While both groups share fundamental concerns about forest sustainability and climate impacts, Tribal respondents consistently frame these issues within contexts of cultural preservation, treaty rights, and intergenerational responsibility, whereas non-Tribal concerns tend to focus more on recreational access, general environmental health, and technical management solutions. The convergence around climate change concerns (expressed by 36% of non-Tribal and 20% of Tribal respondents) indicates potential common ground for collaborative approaches to forest climate adaptation, yet the data suggests that effective strategies must address not only ecological concerns but also the cultural and rights-based dimensions that are particularly important to Tribal communities. The higher proportion of water quality concerns among Tribal respondents (18% vs. 9% for non-Tribal) and the emphasis on cultural access rights highlight the need for climate adaptation strategies that protect both ecosystem services and cultural practices, while the focus on intergenerational responsibility evident in both groups' hopes suggests that long-term forest resilience planning should explicitly incorporate multigenerational perspectives and traditional ecological knowledge alongside scientific management approaches.

4. Discussions and Conclusion

This survey reveals important insights into how Tribal and non-Tribal communities interact with forests, experience climate-related changes, and envision forest stewardship for the future. The findings illuminate both shared values and distinct vulnerabilities that carry significant implications for forest management and policy.

Forests serve as vital resources for both groups, but the depth and nature of these relationships differ fundamentally. Tribal participants demonstrated significantly higher engagement in culturally rooted practices including hunting, fishing, gathering medicinal plants, and making ceremonial items. This pattern reflects the deep cultural and subsistence connections that Indigenous communities maintain with forest ecosystems, consistent with KBIC's long-standing traditions of stewardship and the rights protected under the 1842 Treaty of La Pointe (KBIC NRD, 2013; Dockry et al., 2022).

Non-Tribal participants more frequently emphasized recreational use and environmental benefits such as clean air and water. While both groups highly value forests for spiritual well-being, fresh air, clean water, and recreation, Tribal participants placed significantly greater importance on forests for identity, cultural heritage, medicinal plants, commercial income, and knowledge transmission. These differences underscore that for Indigenous communities, forests function as integrated cultural, economic, and ecological foundations rather than primarily recreational spaces.

The survey documented widespread awareness of environmental change, but impacts were unevenly distributed. Tribal participants reported significantly higher rates of decline in culturally important

species, particularly berries and fish, which serve as both traditional food sources and cultural keystone resources. They also experienced more negative impacts on their ability to gather medicinal plants and materials for traditional items. These patterns reflect a fundamental vulnerability: communities with deeper reliance on specific forest resources face disproportionately severe consequences when those resources are disrupted (STACCWG, 2021). Climate-induced ecological changes threaten not only subsistence practices but also knowledge transmission and cultural continuity. However, the survey also revealed Indigenous resilience, with some Tribal respondents reporting that climate challenges have strengthened their spiritual connections and motivated increased knowledge-sharing efforts.

Despite different relationships with forests, both groups expressed remarkably similar concerns and aspirations. Participants across groups identified climate change, invasive species, overharvesting, land privatization, and pollution as primary threats to forest health. Their hopes converged on sustainable management, conservation, education, public access, and respect for Indigenous traditions.

Critically, Tribal participants explicitly linked forest futures to cultural survival and sovereignty. This connection demonstrates that effective forest governance must address ecological health and cultural preservation simultaneously, ensuring that conservation strategies protect biodiversity while sustaining the knowledge systems and practices that have shaped these landscapes for generations.

These findings point to three essential principles for forest stewardship in the region. First, management strategies must be inclusive, recognizing and accommodating both recreational and culturally essential forest uses. Even small ecological shifts can produce outsized consequences for Indigenous communities, requiring management frameworks that prioritize cultural keystone species and ecosystem integrity. Second, resilience must be understood to extend beyond ecological measures to encompass cultural dimensions. Supporting communities' efforts to strengthen spiritual connections and knowledge-sharing represents a crucial component of climate adaptation. Third, the most effective policies will incorporate Indigenous knowledge systems, respect Tribal sovereignty, and explicitly address historical injustices that have limited access to land and resources. Aligning with the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, centering Indigenous voices in forest management will enhance both legitimacy and collaborative stewardship capacity.

This study demonstrates that climate-related change presents both environmental and cultural challenges. The future of regional forests depends on developing strategies that sustain ecological systems while safeguarding the cultural identities, livelihoods, and rights of all dependent communities. For KBIC, these findings will inform the 2025 Natural Resources Harvesting Survey and updates to harvesting regulations, supporting the development of collaborative partnerships that respect Tribal sovereignty and create space for cross-cultural dialogue in forest stewardship.

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Appendix A. Questionnaires

Thank you for taking the time to complete this short survey!

We respectfully request that you provide information about your relationship with landscape and how it changes in your community. The information you provide will be anonymous, meaning not tied to you or your name in any way. The collected information will be compiled and shared with community leaders, including KBIC staff and Tribal Council members.

1. Are you a Tribal member or descendant? If yes, which Tribe:

2. Which state do you currently live? Please indicate village, township, and city.

3. How many winters have you lived?

4. Let us consider a forest an extensive area covered by a variety of trees, wildlife, and other wild plants and medicines. During the last year, how frequently do you visit forests for the activities below?

	Weekly	Biweekly	Monthly	Bimonthly	Once a year	N/A
Hunting						
Fishing						
Trapping						
Medicinal plants gathering						
Gathering plants for traditional food or drink (berries, nuts, roots, leaves, or others)						
Gathering materials for making traditional/ceremonial items (non-commercial use)						
Gathering materials for non-commercial activity (crafting, firewood, boughs, mushroom, maple sap, birch sap, or others)						
Harvesting materials for commercial activity (timber, crafting, firewood, boughs, mushroom, maple sap, birch sap, or others)						
Recreation (wildlife viewing, hiking, snowshoeing, or others)						
Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment						
Sharing your knowledge and skills with others (teaching, education, training,...)						
Other activities:.....						

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5. On a scale from 1 to 10 (1 = very low importance, 10 = very high importance), how important are forests to your.....?

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	N/A
Identity and cultural heritage											
Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment											
Ability to share your knowledge and skills with others (teaching, education, training,...)											
Accessing for fresh air and clean water											
Opportunities for recreation (wildlife viewing, hiking, snowshoeing, or others)											
Accessing for subsistence sources (hunting, trapping, gathering, fishing)											
Accessing for medicinal sources											
Accessing for income source from commercial activity (harvesting timber, fishing, collecting firewood, boughs, mushroom, maple sap, birch sap, or others)											
Other interests:.....											

6. In the last five years, what changes on the landscape did you notice in your community?

	Decrease	Stayed the same	Increase	Not sure
Temperature				
Flooding				
Water level in streams				
Fish population in streams				
Soil erosion				
Snowfall				
Forest cover				
Cedar				
Birch				
Balsam fir				
Maple				
Berries (cranberries, blueberries,...)				
Bear				
Deer				
Ruffed grouse				
Insects				
Human activities				
Other observations:.....				

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7. Compared with the last 5 years, how do the changes on landscape influence your ability for.....?

	Much better	Somewhat better	Stayed the same	Somewhat worse	Much worse	N/A
Hunting						
Fishing						
Trapping						
Medicinal plants gathering						
Gathering plants for traditional food or drink (berries, nuts, roots, leaves, or others)						
Gathering materials for making traditional/ceremonial items (non-commercial use)						
Gathering materials for non-commercial activity (crafting, firewood, boughs, mushroom, maple sap, birch sap, or others)						
Harvesting materials for commercial activity (timber, crafting, firewood, boughs, mushroom, maple sap, birch sap, or others)						
Recreation (wildlife viewing, hiking, snowshoeing, or others)						
Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment						
Sharing your knowledge and skills with others (teaching, education, training,...)						
Other activities:.....						

8. Currently, what are your biggest concerns and/or hopes for the future of the forests?

.....

.....

.....

MIIGWECH

(thank you!)

Please return the form and complete a drawing ticket with your first name and phone number.

Appendix B. Cronbach’s alpha results

Construct	Number of items	Cronbach’s alpha
Frequency of forest interactions	11	0.61
Perceptions on the importance of forests	8	0.77
Observations related to forest cover and plants	6	0.91
Observations related to wildlife, fish, and insects	5	0.78
Observations related to weather patterns and human activities	6	0.71
Influences of climate-related changes on respondents’ livelihoods and cultural aspects	10	0.86

Appendix C. Responses' tables across two groups

Table 3.2. Frequency of visiting forests for different purposes between Tribal and non-Tribal groups

Characteristic	Overall, N = 232¹	Non-Tribal, N = 122¹	Tribal, N = 110¹	p-value²
01.Hunting				0.11
Once a year	53 (23%)	22 (18%)	31 (28%)	
Bimonthly	8 (3.4%)	3 (2.5%)	5 (4.5%)	
Monthly	12 (5.2%)	6 (4.9%)	6 (5.5%)	
Biweekly	3 (1.3%)	0 (0%)	3 (2.7%)	
Weekly	16 (6.9%)	10 (8.2%)	6 (5.5%)	
Not applicable	140 (60%)	81 (66%)	59 (54%)	
02.Fishing				0.12
Once a year	41 (18%)	18 (15%)	23 (21%)	
Bimonthly	31 (13%)	12 (9.8%)	19 (17%)	
Monthly	38 (16%)	23 (19%)	15 (14%)	
Biweekly	8 (3.4%)	2 (1.6%)	6 (5.5%)	
Weekly	23 (9.9%)	14 (11%)	9 (8.2%)	
Not applicable	91 (39%)	53 (43%)	38 (35%)	
03.Trapping				0.3
Once a year	13 (5.6%)	4 (3.3%)	9 (8.2%)	
Bimonthly	2 (0.9%)	2 (1.6%)	0 (0%)	
Monthly	5 (2.2%)	2 (1.6%)	3 (2.7%)	
Biweekly	1 (0.4%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.9%)	
Weekly	7 (3.0%)	3 (2.5%)	4 (3.6%)	
Not applicable	204 (88%)	111 (91%)	93 (85%)	
04.Medicinal plants gathering				0.051
Once a year	34 (15%)	12 (9.8%)	22 (20%)	
Bimonthly	24 (10%)	11 (9.0%)	13 (12%)	
Monthly	25 (11%)	10 (8.2%)	15 (14%)	
Biweekly	5 (2.2%)	2 (1.6%)	3 (2.7%)	
Weekly	14 (6.0%)	7 (5.7%)	7 (6.4%)	
Not applicable	130 (56%)	80 (66%)	50 (45%)	
05.Traditional food or drink				0.11
Once a year	53 (23%)	31 (25%)	22 (20%)	
Bimonthly	36 (16%)	11 (9.0%)	25 (23%)	
Monthly	35 (15%)	18 (15%)	17 (15%)	
Biweekly	10 (4.3%)	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)	
Weekly	19 (8.2%)	10 (8.2%)	9 (8.2%)	
Not applicable	79 (34%)	46 (38%)	33 (30%)	
06.Making traditional /ceremonial items (non-commercial use)				<0.001***
Once a year	31 (13%)	9 (7.4%)	22 (20%)	
Bimonthly	21 (9.1%)	6 (4.9%)	15 (14%)	

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Monthly	26 (11%)	10 (8.2%)	16 (15%)	
Biweekly	3 (1.3%)	1 (0.8%)	2 (1.8%)	
Weekly	9 (3.9%)	1 (0.8%)	8 (7.3%)	
Not applicable	142 (61%)	95 (78%)	47 (43%)	
07. Gathering materials for non-commercial activity				0.3
Once a year	57 (25%)	32 (26%)	25 (23%)	
Bimonthly	37 (16%)	13 (11%)	24 (22%)	
Monthly	39 (17%)	23 (19%)	16 (15%)	
Biweekly	12 (5.2%)	6 (4.9%)	6 (5.5%)	
Weekly	18 (7.8%)	9 (7.4%)	9 (8.2%)	
Not applicable	69 (30%)	39 (32%)	30 (27%)	
08. Harvesting materials for commercial activity				0.3
Once a year	26 (11%)	10 (8.2%)	16 (15%)	
Bimonthly	18 (7.8%)	9 (7.4%)	9 (8.2%)	
Monthly	13 (5.6%)	5 (4.1%)	8 (7.3%)	
Biweekly	3 (1.3%)	1 (0.8%)	2 (1.8%)	
Weekly	10 (4.3%)	4 (3.3%)	6 (5.5%)	
Not applicable	162 (70%)	93 (76%)	69 (63%)	
09. Recreation				0.13
Once a year	22 (9.5%)	8 (6.6%)	14 (13%)	
Bimonthly	24 (10%)	12 (9.8%)	12 (11%)	
Monthly	39 (17%)	22 (18%)	17 (15%)	
Biweekly	32 (14%)	17 (14%)	15 (14%)	
Weekly	91 (39%)	55 (45%)	36 (33%)	
Not applicable	24 (10%)	8 (6.6%)	16 (15%)	
10. Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment				0.2
Once a year	19 (8.2%)	7 (5.7%)	12 (11%)	
Bimonthly	15 (6.5%)	11 (9.0%)	4 (3.6%)	
Monthly	29 (13%)	13 (11%)	16 (15%)	
Biweekly	28 (12%)	16 (13%)	12 (11%)	
Weekly	98 (42%)	49 (40%)	49 (45%)	
Not applicable	43 (19%)	26 (21%)	17 (15%)	
11. Sharing knowledge and skills with others (teaching, education, training...)				0.3
Once a year	29 (13%)	13 (11%)	16 (15%)	
Bimonthly	22 (9.5%)	10 (8.2%)	12 (11%)	
Monthly	37 (16%)	23 (19%)	14 (13%)	
Biweekly	12 (5.2%)	4 (3.3%)	8 (7.3%)	
Weekly	51 (22%)	24 (20%)	27 (25%)	
Not applicable	81 (35%)	48 (39%)	33 (30%)	

¹Median (IQR); n (%)

²Fisher's exact test; Pearson's Chi-squared test.

Significant codes: 0'****' 0.001'***' 0.01'**'

Table 3.3. Importance of forests to livelihood and cultural aspects of Tribal and non-Tribal groups

Characteristic	Overall, N = 232¹	Non-Tribal, N = 122¹	Tribal, N = 110¹	p-value²
01.Identity and cultural heritage				0.004**
1 – Not at all important	10 (4.3%)	8 (6.6%)	2 (1.8%)	
2	2 (0.9%)	1 (0.8%)	1 (0.9%)	
3	7 (3.0%)	5 (4.1%)	2 (1.8%)	
4	3 (1.3%)	2 (1.6%)	1 (0.9%)	
5	14 (6.0%)	11 (9.0%)	3 (2.7%)	
6	9 (3.9%)	5 (4.1%)	4 (3.6%)	
7	15 (6.5%)	8 (6.6%)	7 (6.4%)	
8	22 (9.5%)	13 (11%)	9 (8.2%)	
9	14 (6.0%)	8 (6.6%)	6 (5.5%)	
10 – Extremely important	117 (50%)	45 (37%)	72 (65%)	
Not applicable	19 (8.2%)	16 (13%)	3 (2.7%)	
02.Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment				0.2
1 – Not at all important	5 (2.2%)	4 (3.3%)	1 (0.9%)	
2	2 (0.9%)	1 (0.8%)	1 (0.9%)	
3	3 (1.3%)	2 (1.6%)	1 (0.9%)	
4	2 (0.9%)	2 (1.6%)	0 (0%)	
5	8 (3.4%)	3 (2.5%)	5 (4.5%)	
6	9 (3.9%)	4 (3.3%)	5 (4.5%)	
7	7 (3.0%)	4 (3.3%)	3 (2.7%)	
8	26 (11%)	17 (14%)	9 (8.2%)	
9	20 (8.6%)	11 (9.0%)	9 (8.2%)	
10 – Extremely important	138 (59%)	64 (52%)	74 (67%)	
Not applicable	12 (5.2%)	10 (8.2%)	2 (1.8%)	
03.Ability to share knowledge and skills				0.029*
1 – Not at all important	5 (2.2%)	4 (3.3%)	1 (0.9%)	
2	10 (4.3%)	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)	
3	13 (5.6%)	6 (4.9%)	7 (6.4%)	
4	5 (2.2%)	3 (2.5%)	2 (1.8%)	
5	22 (9.5%)	18 (15%)	4 (3.6%)	
6	6 (2.6%)	3 (2.5%)	3 (2.7%)	
7	18 (7.8%)	8 (6.6%)	10 (9.1%)	
8	18 (7.8%)	9 (7.4%)	9 (8.2%)	
9	20 (8.6%)	12 (9.8%)	8 (7.3%)	
10 – Extremely important	91 (39%)	36 (30%)	55 (50%)	
Not applicable	24 (10%)	17 (14%)	7 (6.4%)	

04. Accessing for fresh air and clean water

0.5

1 – Not at all important	5 (2.2%)	4 (3.3%)	1 (0.9%)
2	1 (0.4%)	1 (0.8%)	0 (0%)
3	2 (0.9%)	0 (0%)	2 (1.8%)
4	1 (0.4%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.9%)
5	1 (0.4%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.9%)
6	4 (1.7%)	2 (1.6%)	2 (1.8%)
7	5 (2.2%)	3 (2.5%)	2 (1.8%)
8	10 (4.3%)	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)
9	15 (6.5%)	10 (8.2%)	5 (4.5%)
10 – Extremely important	177 (76%)	89 (73%)	88 (80%)
Not applicable	11 (4.7%)	7 (5.7%)	4 (3.6%)

05. Opportunities for recreation

0.082

1 – Not at all important	4 (1.7%)	4 (3.3%)	0 (0%)
2	1 (0.4%)	1 (0.8%)	0 (0%)
3	2 (0.9%)	1 (0.8%)	1 (0.9%)
4	2 (0.9%)	0 (0%)	2 (1.8%)
5	6 (2.6%)	0 (0%)	6 (5.5%)
6	3 (1.3%)	2 (1.6%)	1 (0.9%)
7	8 (3.4%)	3 (2.5%)	5 (4.5%)
8	23 (9.9%)	12 (9.8%)	11 (10%)
9	22 (9.5%)	12 (9.8%)	10 (9.1%)
10 – Extremely important	155 (67%)	82 (67%)	73 (66%)
Not applicable	6 (2.6%)	5 (4.1%)	1 (0.9%)

06. Accessing for subsistence sources

0.14

1 – Not at all important	13 (5.6%)	8 (6.6%)	5 (4.5%)
2	14 (6.0%)	11 (9.0%)	3 (2.7%)
3	7 (3.0%)	5 (4.1%)	2 (1.8%)
4	3 (1.3%)	1 (0.8%)	2 (1.8%)
5	13 (5.6%)	7 (5.7%)	6 (5.5%)
6	8 (3.4%)	6 (4.9%)	2 (1.8%)
7	7 (3.0%)	2 (1.6%)	5 (4.5%)
8	19 (8.2%)	10 (8.2%)	9 (8.2%)
9	15 (6.5%)	8 (6.6%)	7 (6.4%)
10 – Extremely important	108 (47%)	47 (39%)	61 (55%)
Not applicable	25 (11%)	17 (14%)	8 (7.3%)

07. Accessing for medicinal source

0.053

1 – Not at all important	23 (9.9%)	16 (13%)	7 (6.4%)
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2	12 (5.2%)	10 (8.2%)	2 (1.8%)
3	13 (5.6%)	8 (6.6%)	5 (4.5%)
4	6 (2.6%)	3 (2.5%)	3 (2.7%)
5	16 (6.9%)	9 (7.4%)	7 (6.4%)
6	10 (4.3%)	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)
7	8 (3.4%)	5 (4.1%)	3 (2.7%)
8	11 (4.7%)	6 (4.9%)	5 (4.5%)
9	10 (4.3%)	5 (4.1%)	5 (4.5%)
10 – Extremely important	97 (42%)	37 (30%)	60 (55%)
Not applicable	26 (11%)	17 (14%)	9 (8.2%)

0.048*

08. Accessing for income source from commercial activity

1 – Not at all important	36 (16%)	25 (20%)	11 (10%)
2	11 (4.7%)	6 (4.9%)	5 (4.5%)
3	7 (3.0%)	4 (3.3%)	3 (2.7%)
4	9 (3.9%)	6 (4.9%)	3 (2.7%)
5	13 (5.6%)	4 (3.3%)	9 (8.2%)
6	6 (2.6%)	1 (0.8%)	5 (4.5%)
7	4 (1.7%)	1 (0.8%)	3 (2.7%)
8	12 (5.2%)	4 (3.3%)	8 (7.3%)
9	14 (6.0%)	10 (8.2%)	4 (3.6%)
10 – Extremely important	66 (28%)	29 (24%)	37 (34%)
Not applicable	54 (23%)	32 (26%)	22 (20%)

¹Median (IQR); n (%)

²Fisher’s exact test; Pearson’s Chi-squared test.

Significant codes: 0‘****’ 0.001‘***’ 0.01‘**’

Table 3.4.1. Changes in landscape reported by surveyed participants.

Characteristic	Overall, N = 232 ¹	Non-Tribal, N = 122 ¹	Tribal, N = 110 ¹	p-value ²
01. Forest cover				0.6
Decrease	82 (35%)	44 (36%)	38 (35%)	
Stayed the same	67 (29%)	39 (32%)	28 (25%)	
Increase	14 (6.0%)	6 (4.9%)	8 (7.3%)	
Not sure	69 (30%)	33 (27%)	36 (33%)	
02. Cedar				0.8
Decrease	46 (20%)	22 (18%)	24 (22%)	
Stayed the same	76 (33%)	39 (32%)	37 (34%)	
Increase	4 (1.7%)	2 (1.6%)	2 (1.8%)	
Not sure	106 (46%)	59 (48%)	47 (43%)	
03. Birch				0.5
Decrease	59 (25%)	27 (22%)	32 (29%)	
Stayed the same	73 (31%)	37 (30%)	36 (33%)	
Increase	4 (1.7%)	2 (1.6%)	2 (1.8%)	

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Not sure	96 (41%)	56 (46%)	40 (36%)	
04.Balsam fir				0.8
Decrease	25 (11%)	12 (9.8%)	13 (12%)	
Stayed the same	84 (36%)	46 (38%)	38 (35%)	
Increase	6 (2.6%)	4 (3.3%)	2 (1.8%)	
Not sure	117 (50%)	60 (49%)	57 (52%)	
05.Maple				0.4
Decrease	26 (11%)	10 (8.2%)	16 (15%)	
Stayed the same	77 (33%)	42 (34%)	35 (32%)	
Increase	22 (9.5%)	14 (11%)	8 (7.3%)	
Not sure	107 (46%)	56 (46%)	51 (46%)	
06.Berries				0.026*
Decrease	57 (25%)	21 (17%)	36 (33%)	
Stayed the same	77 (33%)	46 (38%)	31 (28%)	
Increase	14 (6.0%)	10 (8.2%)	4 (3.6%)	
Not sure	84 (36%)	45 (37%)	39 (35%)	
07.Bear				0.2
Decrease	34 (15%)	17 (14%)	17 (15%)	
Stayed the same	49 (21%)	30 (25%)	19 (17%)	
Increase	32 (14%)	12 (9.8%)	20 (18%)	
Not sure	117 (50%)	63 (52%)	54 (49%)	
08.Deer				>0.9
Decrease	32 (14%)	17 (14%)	15 (14%)	
Stayed the same	62 (27%)	32 (26%)	30 (27%)	
Increase	73 (31%)	40 (33%)	33 (30%)	
Not sure	65 (28%)	33 (27%)	32 (29%)	
09.Ruffed grouse				0.4
Decrease	30 (13%)	16 (13%)	14 (13%)	
Stayed the same	51 (22%)	31 (25%)	20 (18%)	
Increase	22 (9.5%)	9 (7.4%)	13 (12%)	
Not sure	129 (56%)	66 (54%)	63 (57%)	
10.Fish population in streams				0.033*
Decrease	73 (31%)	37 (30%)	36 (33%)	
Stayed the same	47 (20%)	31 (25%)	16 (15%)	
Increase	11 (4.7%)	2 (1.6%)	9 (8.2%)	
Not sure	101 (44%)	52 (43%)	49 (45%)	
11.Insects				0.8
Decrease	25 (11%)	15 (12%)	10 (9.1%)	
Stayed the same	41 (18%)	20 (16%)	21 (19%)	
Increase	94 (41%)	49 (40%)	45 (41%)	
Not sure	72 (31%)	38 (31%)	34 (31%)	
12.Temperature				0.7
Decrease	17 (7.3%)	7 (5.7%)	10 (9.1%)	
Stayed the same	39 (17%)	22 (18%)	17 (15%)	
Increase	150 (65%)	80 (66%)	70 (64%)	
Not sure	26 (11%)	13 (11%)	13 (12%)	

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13.Flooding				0.3
Decrease	10 (4.3%)	3 (2.5%)	7 (6.4%)	
Stayed the same	61 (26%)	36 (30%)	25 (23%)	
Increase	116 (50%)	58 (48%)	58 (53%)	
Not sure	45 (19%)	25 (20%)	20 (18%)	
14.Water level in streams				0.12
Decrease	58 (25%)	33 (27%)	25 (23%)	
Stayed the same	54 (23%)	34 (28%)	20 (18%)	
Increase	73 (31%)	31 (25%)	42 (38%)	
Not sure	47 (20%)	24 (20%)	23 (21%)	
15.Snowfall				0.5
Decrease	86 (37%)	44 (36%)	42 (38%)	
Stayed the same	63 (27%)	38 (31%)	25 (23%)	
Increase	53 (23%)	26 (21%)	27 (25%)	
Not sure	30 (13%)	14 (11%)	16 (15%)	
16.Soil erosion				0.053
Decrease	15 (6.5%)	3 (2.5%)	12 (11%)	
Stayed the same	39 (17%)	24 (20%)	15 (14%)	
Increase	108 (47%)	58 (48%)	50 (45%)	
Not sure	70 (30%)	37 (30%)	33 (30%)	
17.Human activities				0.6
Decrease	13 (5.6%)	7 (5.7%)	6 (5.5%)	
Stayed the same	40 (17%)	25 (20%)	15 (14%)	
Increase	125 (54%)	63 (52%)	62 (56%)	
Not sure	54 (23%)	27 (22%)	27 (25%)	

¹Median (IQR); n (%)

²Fisher's exact test; Pearson's Chi-squared test.

Significant codes: 0'****' 0.001'***' 0.01'**'

Table 3.4.2. Influence of climate-related changes on different livelihood and cultural aspects across Tribal and non-Tribal groups.

Characteristic	Overall, N = 232 ¹	Non-Tribal, N = 122 ¹	Tribal, N = 110 ¹	p-value ²
01.Hunting				0.057
Much worse	8 (3.4%)	3 (2.5%)	5 (4.5%)	
Somewhat worse	33 (14%)	13 (11%)	20 (18%)	
Stayed the same	54 (23%)	25 (20%)	29 (26%)	
Somewhat better	14 (6.0%)	8 (6.6%)	6 (5.5%)	
Much better	3 (1.3%)	0 (0%)	3 (2.7%)	
Not applicable	120 (52%)	73 (60%)	47 (43%)	
02.Fishing				0.12
Much worse	7 (3.0%)	3 (2.5%)	4 (3.6%)	
Somewhat worse	37 (16%)	21 (17%)	16 (15%)	
Stayed the same	69 (30%)	35 (29%)	34 (31%)	
Somewhat better	12 (5.2%)	3 (2.5%)	9 (8.2%)	

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Much better	6 (2.6%)	1 (0.8%)	5 (4.5%)	
Not applicable	101 (44%)	59 (48%)	42 (38%)	
03.Trapping				0.4
Much worse	6 (2.6%)	2 (1.6%)	4 (3.6%)	
Somewhat worse	10 (4.3%)	5 (4.1%)	5 (4.5%)	
Stayed the same	32 (14%)	15 (12%)	17 (15%)	
Somewhat better	5 (2.2%)	2 (1.6%)	3 (2.7%)	
Much better	3 (1.3%)	0 (0%)	3 (2.7%)	
Not applicable	176 (76%)	98 (80%)	78 (71%)	
04.Medicinal plants gathering				0.006**
Much worse	7 (3.0%)	3 (2.5%)	4 (3.6%)	
Somewhat worse	37 (16%)	12 (9.8%)	25 (23%)	
Stayed the same	55 (24%)	25 (20%)	30 (27%)	
Somewhat better	10 (4.3%)	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)	
Much better	5 (2.2%)	1 (0.8%)	4 (3.6%)	
Not applicable	118 (51%)	75 (61%)	43 (39%)	
05.Traditional food or drink				0.4
Much worse	9 (3.9%)	4 (3.3%)	5 (4.5%)	
Somewhat worse	36 (16%)	15 (12%)	21 (19%)	
Stayed the same	80 (34%)	42 (34%)	38 (35%)	
Somewhat better	16 (6.9%)	8 (6.6%)	8 (7.3%)	
Much better	6 (2.6%)	2 (1.6%)	4 (3.6%)	
Not applicable	85 (37%)	51 (42%)	34 (31%)	
06.Making traditional /ceremonial items (non-commercial use)				0.018*
Much worse	8 (3.4%)	2 (1.6%)	6 (5.5%)	
Somewhat worse	23 (9.9%)	7 (5.7%)	16 (15%)	
Stayed the same	58 (25%)	28 (23%)	30 (27%)	
Somewhat better	11 (4.7%)	5 (4.1%)	6 (5.5%)	
Much better	4 (1.7%)	1 (0.8%)	3 (2.7%)	
Not applicable	128 (55%)	79 (65%)	49 (45%)	
07.Gathering materials for non-commercial activity				0.2
Much worse	8 (3.4%)	2 (1.6%)	6 (5.5%)	
Somewhat worse	32 (14%)	14 (11%)	18 (16%)	
Stayed the same	83 (36%)	49 (40%)	34 (31%)	
Somewhat better	10 (4.3%)	6 (4.9%)	4 (3.6%)	
Much better	6 (2.6%)	1 (0.8%)	5 (4.5%)	
Not applicable	93 (40%)	50 (41%)	43 (39%)	
08.Harvesting materials for commercial activity				0.6
Much worse	7 (3.0%)	2 (1.6%)	5 (4.5%)	
Somewhat worse	21 (9.1%)	9 (7.4%)	12 (11%)	
Stayed the same	47 (20%)	27 (22%)	20 (18%)	
Somewhat better	12 (5.2%)	6 (4.9%)	6 (5.5%)	

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Much better	5 (2.2%)	2 (1.6%)	3 (2.7%)	
Not applicable	140 (60%)	76 (62%)	64 (58%)	
09.Recreation				0.6
Much worse	7 (3.0%)	3 (2.5%)	4 (3.6%)	
Somewhat worse	58 (25%)	31 (25%)	27 (25%)	
Stayed the same	90 (39%)	53 (43%)	37 (34%)	
Somewhat better	26 (11%)	13 (11%)	13 (12%)	
Much better	15 (6.5%)	7 (5.7%)	8 (7.3%)	
Not applicable	36 (16%)	15 (12%)	21 (19%)	
10.Spiritual well-being and personal enrichment				0.7
Much worse	8 (3.4%)	4 (3.3%)	4 (3.6%)	
Somewhat worse	46 (20%)	26 (21%)	20 (18%)	
Stayed the same	90 (39%)	51 (42%)	39 (35%)	
Somewhat better	24 (10%)	11 (9.0%)	13 (12%)	
Much better	20 (8.6%)	8 (6.6%)	12 (11%)	
Not applicable	44 (19%)	22 (18%)	22 (20%)	
11.Sharing knowledge and skills with others (teaching, education, training...)				0.084
Much worse	8 (3.4%)	4 (3.3%)	4 (3.6%)	
Somewhat worse	22 (9.5%)	10 (8.2%)	12 (11%)	
Stayed the same	76 (33%)	48 (39%)	28 (25%)	
Somewhat better	26 (11%)	12 (9.8%)	14 (13%)	
Much better	19 (8.2%)	5 (4.1%)	14 (13%)	
Not applicable	81 (35%)	43 (35%)	38 (35%)	

¹Median (IQR); n (%)

²Fisher's exact test

Significant codes: 0'****' 0.001'***' 0.01'**'

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